

Hydrated Electron, Its Structure and Some Studies of Its Reactions*

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The discovery of the electron at the turn of the century by Sir J. J. Thomson (1897) opened new experimental and conceptual chapters in chemistry and physics. This particle is an essential element of quantum mechanical theories of atomic and molecular energy levels, intramolecular forces and valency. It is not only considered a constituent of matter in theoretical studies but is also utilized in experimental physics as a bombarding particle in studies related to structure of matter.

The existence in solution of charged particles, positive and negative, which could move about freely and independently was postulated even earlier (1834) by Faraday¹. For many years, electrochemists and inorganic chemists concerned with electrode processes and oxidation reduction reactions, primarily in aqueous solution have written hypothetical reversible processes, such as (1) and (2), involving an electron and have associated with these processes values of reaction potentials in volts.

In recent years it has been recognised that in water or other polar solvent we may have the simplest ion of all, the electron itself. The idea that electron might exist as an independent species in solution dates back to 1908 when Kraus² suggested that it was present as an independent identity in solutions of alkali metals in liquid ammonia. He ascribed the blue colouration and the very high electrical conductivity of solutions of alkali metals in liquid ammonia to the presence of ammoniated electrons, but since hydrogen is evolved immediately when sodium is added to water it was assumed that the aqueous counterpart did not exist.

In 1939 Randall³ wrote that the electron might as well be considered a chemical element. He went on to say that "the elementary particle of electricity, the electron, may be regarded as an element of nuclear mass zero, atomic number zero and electric charge of -1 ". Developments in the past decade have added support to Randall's idea that electron may indeed be treated as an element. Now with the discovery of e^-_{aq} , we complete the series of negative ions, e^-_{aq} , H^- , F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and At^- .

* Presidential address delivered at annual general meeting held at Madras on December. 1, 1970.

1. M. Faraday, *Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc.* (London), 1834, **124**, 77.
2. C. A. Kraus, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **30**, 1323.
3. Randall, *Amer. Phys. Teacher*, 1939, **7**, 292.

The concept of hydrated electrons was first invoked by G. Stein⁴, an aqueous radiation chemist working with J. Weiss. Just about the same time, the theoretical radiation chemist, Platzman⁵ indicated that there is a definite probability that an electron, born in the process of ionization when high energy radiation interacts with matter, on thermalization, may get trapped and solvated with the surrounding solvent in a polar medium.

But despite these early suggestions most of the practising radiation chemists did not realize the importance of hydrated electrons and these were continued to be mistaken for H atoms for almost a decade. They were all satisfied with the concept of the excited water molecule formation and its decomposition to free radicals. For example, in the case of water.

It was implicitly assumed that the back neutralisation reaction would be too rapid and the coulombic force of the sibling positive hole too great even to consider the existence of separated ions.

Experimentally also an early attempt by Linschitz⁶ and by Allen⁷ at detection of e^-_{aq} failed.

Samuel and Magee⁸ developed an admirable diffusion model involving hydrogen atoms and OH radicals formed by the rapid neutralisation of the thermalised electrons in a time too short for solvation to occur. Because the diffusion model explained the radical and molecular yields and their dependence on linear energy transfer (LET), there was no cause before 1958 to doubt that radiation chemical effect in water resulted simply from the process $\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H} + \text{OH}$.

Need for the existence of another reducing species : At about this time from different laboratories evidence started forthcoming indicating the need of an additional reducing species in addition to H atoms. In 1958 Baxendale and Hughes⁹ noted an extraordinarily large effect shown by Fe^{+3} and Cu^{+2} ions on the yields of hydrogen from irradiated aqueous methanol solution. Hydrogen gas produced in the reaction

4. G. Stein, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1952, 12, 227.
5. R. L. Platzman, Physical and Chemical aspects of Basic mechanisms in Radiobiology, *Natl. Res. Council Publ.*, 1953, 305, 34.
6. H. Linschitz, Physical and chemical aspects of Basic mechanisms in Radiobiology, *Natl. Res. Council Publ.*, 1953, 305, 39.
7. R. Roberts and A. O. Allen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1256
8. A. H. Samuel and J. L. Magee, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, 21, 1080.
9. J. H. Baxendale and G. Hughes, *Z. Physik. Chem. (N.F.)*, 1958, 14, 323.

was reduced by Fe^{+3} to a much greater extent than the competitive reaction

would predict. It was conjectured that Fe^{+3} are intercepting some other species present in the system which might be a precursor of H atoms

At about the same time Hayon and Weiss¹⁰ showed that an alteration of the $p\text{H}$ of an aqueous solution of monochloroacetic acid gave rise to different products. In acid solutions H_2 was the predominant product as expected, whereas Cl^- was favoured at $p\text{H} > 4$. Their results are reproduced in Figure-1 which shows the competition at $p\text{H} = 1$ between H^+ and ClCH_2COOH for e^-_{aq} . At low concentration of chloroacetic acid, reaction

predominates in which e^-_{aq} are converted into H atoms and H_2 is produced by the reaction

FIG. 1 Dependence of initial yields upon concentration of monochloroacetic acid at $p\text{H} 1.0$ (⁸)

At high concentration of solute e^-_{aq} are scavenged by ClCH_2COOH

It was also shown that H atoms generated by an electrodeless discharge and passed into chloroacetic acid solution produced H_2 via the above reaction, corroborating the designation of the acidic species as H and implying that at $p\text{H} > 4$ another reducing species is produced.

10. E. Hayon and J. J. Weiss, *Proc. U.N. Internal. Conf. Peaceful uses Atomic Energy*, 2nd Geneva, 1958, 29, 80.

Concurrently Barr and Allen¹¹ discovered that the rate constant ratio for the H atoms formed in the reaction $\text{H}_2 + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{H} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and for the reducing species formed in the irradiation of water with H_2O_2 :

$$\frac{k(e^-_{aq} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2)}{k(\text{H} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2)} \quad \text{was found to be 500.}$$

These experiments revealed the participation of two different reducing species in irradiated aqueous solutions. While there was no doubt that the species dominant in neutral and alkaline solutions was e^-_{aq} , proof was still lacking.

Unit negative charge : Although pH dependence of radiation chemical yield indicated that the other reducing species should have a negative charge, the clinching proof was only obtained by the use of Brönsted-Bjerrum theory of ionic reactions^{12,13}. This theory states that the rate constant k at ionic strength μ will vary with ionic strength of the solution according to the equation

$$\log_{10} k/k_0 = 1.02(Z_{e^-_{aq}})(Z_s)\{\mu^{1/2}/[1 + \alpha(\mu^{1/2})]\}$$

where k_0 is the rate constant at zero ionic strength and $Z_{e^-_{aq}}$ and Z_s are the charges on e^-_{aq} and the solutes respectively. Since the expected value for $Z_{e^-_{aq}}$ is -1 , k will increase if Z_s is negative, the rate will be unchanged if Z_s is 0, and the rate will decrease with increasing ionic strength if Z_s is positive.

FIG 2. Effect of ionic strength on relative rate constants of e^-_{aq} reactions. Triangles, $\text{KFe}(\text{CN})_5^{2-}$ relative to N_2O ; circles with the cross, O_2 relative to H_2O_2 ; half solid circles, H^+ relative to H_2O_2 . Open circles, NO_2^- relative to H_2O_2 and squares, $-\text{Ag}^+$ relative to $\text{CH}_2 = \text{CH} - \text{CONH}_2$ (data of Czapski and Schwarz, 1962, Collinson et al, 1962)

11. N. F. Barr and A. O. Allen, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **63**, 928.
12. G. Czapski and H. A. Schwartz, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 471.
13. E. Collinson, F. S. Dainton, D. R. Smith and S. Tazuki, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 140; F. S. Dainton and W. S. Watt, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1963, **A275**, 447.

Because in 1962, when these experiments were planned, the absolute rate constants for these reactions were not known, reliance had to be placed on relative rate constants. Figure-2 shows that a behaviour consistent with $Z_{e^{-aq}} = -1$ is obtained. In each of these curves the reaction rate of the indicated molecule or ion (A) is compared with that of a neutral molecule (B) whose rate is unaffected by ionic strength (that is, each curve represents the ratio of the rate constant of A and B). Relative rate constants are given as a function of ionic strength. The straight lines are drawn with slopes of $+1.02$ for NO_2^- , $+2.04$ for $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{-2}$ and -1.02 for H^+ and Ag^+ . These data are summarized in Table I. No effect is expected, nor was any found for the neutral oxygen molecule.

TABLE I

Behaviour consistent with $Z_{e^{-aq}} = -1$

Solute		Z_A	Slope	$Z_{e^{-aq}}$
A	B			
NO_2^-	H_2O_2	-1	+1.02	-1
O_2	H_2O_2	0	0.0	-1
H^+	H_2O_2	+1	-1.02	-1
$\text{KFe}(\text{CN})_6^{--}$	N_2O	-2	+2.04	-1

Spectrum of e^{-aq} : Platzman⁵ had predicted as early as 1953 that if a thermalized electron gets hydrated then (i) its hydration energy would be about 2.0 eV and (ii) it would absorb in the red part of the spectrum. But the question of its natural life time was not settled. If the half life is approximately 10^{-11} sec or even 10^{-9} sec, as earlier estimates indicated, it would have been impossible to detect e^{-aq} with spectroscopic means then available. Earlier attempts to locate a transient spectrum in x-ray pulsed water or to find the enhanced conductivity expected from the solvated e^{-aq} in irradiated ammonia failed because of low intensity employed^{6,7}.

For this reason the discovery of e^{-aq} was delayed until the present era of high electron current pulsed accelerators and fast reaction techniques. By synchronising an electron pulse with light flash absorption spectrophotometry the spectrum of absorbing transient species generated in the water can be obtained. It was in this way that the spectrum of e^{-aq} was discovered by Boag and Hart^{14,15,16}.

The quartz cell (fig. 3) was irradiated from the side with a ribbon of 1.8 MeV electrons in a pulse of $2 \mu\text{sec}$ duration. Simultaneously with irradiation by this pulse of electrons a uranium spark light source was triggered, and a pulse of continuous light of some 5 micro-seconds duration was passed through the cell and into a spectrograph. The resulting

14. E. J. Hart and J. W. Boag, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 4090.

15. J. W. Boag and E. J. Hart, *Nature*, 1963, **197**, 45.

16. J. P. Keene, *Nature*, 1963, **197**, 47.

spectrum was recorded on a photographic plate. This spectrum and curves showing differences in optical density of irradiated 0.05 *M* sodium carbonate and pure water are shown in fig. 4.

FIG 3 Schematic diagram of apparatus used for kinetic absorption spectroscopy. Insert shows the construction of the absorption cell in greater detail [Reprinted from Hart and Boag, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 84, 4090 (1962)]

Spectrum *a* is from a flash that occurred before irradiation, *b* is from a flash that occurred simultaneously with the electron pulse, and *c* is from a flash that occurred 30 seconds after the electron pulse. The darkened section (above 4500 Å) shows the intense absorption due

FIG 4 Absorption band due to e_{aq}^- in irradiated solutions (a) irradiated 0.05M Na_2CO_3 [mean dose, 7krad (1rad=100erg/g)], (b) pure deaerated water. Insert is the red end of the spectrum: a flash before irradiation, b, flash simultaneous with electron pulse, showing intense absorption due to e_{aq}^- , and c, flash 30 seconds after electron pulse (data of Boag and Hart, 1963, Hart and Boag, 1962).

to the transient e_{aq}^- . A well defined maxima occurs near 7000 Å. Later Keene¹⁷ demonstrated by spectrophotometry that the absorption band was a single structureless one and extended below 3000 to beyond 8000 Å (fig. 5)

Only a trace of the spectrum remains on a photograph taken 25 $\mu\text{sec.}$ after the electron pulse. Consequently, under these conditions the $\tau_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of the e_{aq}^- is less than 25 $\mu\text{sec.}$ Because

of this extremely short half life its identification was delayed until pulse radiolysis technique was developed.

FIG 5 Absorption spectrum of the hydrated electron (data of Fielden and Hart, 1967b, Gordon and Hart, 1964, Keene, 1964)

The evidence supporting the assignment that this transient spectrum is that of hydrated electrons rests on its physical and chemical properties

(i) In shape the absorption band is very similar to that of the classical solvated electron formed by dissolving alkali metals in liquid ammonia (ii) Chemical scavenging evidence clinched the argument. Radiation chemists who since 1958 were aware of two reducing species in irradiated water, knew that H^+ , N_2O , CO_2 , H_2O_2 , O_2 , to mention a few, were powerful scavengers of one of the reducing species. These compounds too were found to be powerful attenuators of the absorption band described above

Rather than by spectrophotography, hydrated electron studies are more simply and accurately carried out by spectrophotometry. Here we obtain the change in concentration as a function of time. This method is ideal for measuring rate constants

Fig 6 Diagram of the pulsed radiolysis experimental lay out [Reprinted from Thomas et al, J of Phys Chem 68, 1524 (1964)]

A typical spectrophotometry system appears in figure 6.

In this apparatus a short pulse of 15 Mev electrons from an accelerator passes through the thin plane mirror E and reaction cell D. Optically absorbing species formed by the pulse absorb some of the continuous light emitted from lamp A. The light from the lamp, focussed by lens B passes back and forth through cell D by reflections from mirrors C and E. In the illustrated assembly, four light passes through the cell are obtained. In a modified unit upto 24 light passes have been incorporated^{17a}. The light reflected from F is focussed on to the slits of a monochromator G and then the selected wavelengths pass into a shielded photo-multiplier tube, the signal from which is amplified, displayed on an oscilloscope and photographed.

Other methods of production : Although the radiolysis of water is unquestionably the most direct and convenient method devised for generating e^-_{aq} it is valuable to compare the spectrum and reactivity so obtained with e^-_{aq} produced in other ways. Some other possible methods of producing e^-_{aq} are discussed.

1. *Sodium amalgam in water* : The reaction of sodium with water is described classically by reaction

followed by the combination of two hydrogen atoms to form molecular hydrogen. If by analogy with NH_3 the first step involves ionization with the formation of e^-_{aq} which survives long enough to become solvated then hydrogen will be formed as

Because the magnitude of k_2 is very large, the spectrophotometric detection of e^-_{aq} under steady state conditions is not feasible. However, it was possible to test the presence of e^-_{aq} chemically. Indeed the presence of nitrous oxide in water (into which dispersed sodium amalgam was added), inhibited the formation of hydrogen with the concurrent generation of nitrogen¹⁸ by reaction

2. *Electrolysis* : Walker¹⁹ showed that hydrated electrons exist near platinum, the electrode in the electrolysis of water, and contrary to general belief, the H atoms are not the principal reducing species. At a current density of $50 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ nitrous oxide lowers the hydrogen yield in a neutral solution at a smooth platinum cathode to about 35% of its N_2O free value. Thus the primary reaction at the cathode is

As expected in acid solutions no nitrogen was formed.

17a. J. Rabani, W. A. Mulac and M. S. Matheson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 53.

18. D. C. Walker, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1966, **44**, 2226.

19. D. C. Walker, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1967, **45**, 807.

3. *Inorganic salts* : Any reducing ion of an electrolytic couple more positive than 0.414 eV may liberate H_2 . A good example is when uranium trichloride dissolves in water, hydrogen is evolved. However, in nitrous oxide solutions nitrogen partially replaces hydrogen. Part of the hydrogen therefore is formed through the intermediate hydrated electrons. Walker¹⁸ explained these results by assuming the primary step as

4. *Hydrogen atoms and free radicals* : Hydrogen atoms and certain organic free radicals may also produce e^-_{aq} . Free radicals may be stabilised by either a gain or loss of an electron. Consequently, free radicals with relatively low electron affinity may act as electron donors, and when stabilised by bond formation may form e^-_{aq} . A clear example of such a process is the equilibrium

This production of e^-_{aq} was verified by absorption spectrophotometry by Matheson and Rabani²⁰. Another reaction of H atoms

has been demonstrated²¹ and verified by Anbar and Hart²²

5. *Photolysis* : The photochemical release of the hydrated electron from halide ions was first proved by competition kinetics²³. Later spectroscopic studies²⁴ confirmed this result in these and in other inorganic and organic ions. Flash photolysis of aqueous solutions of I^- , $Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$, phenol, cresol, etc.²⁵, has been shown to produce a transient species having the same absorption spectrum and reactivity as e^-_{aq} . Further studies on the mechanism of these negative ion reactions indicate first a bound excited state of the ion, then a geminate pair and finally a neutral atom and the hydrated electron.

Stein²⁶ estimated the life time of the excited ion $I^-^*_{aq}$ at about 10^{-10} sec.

Recently in our own laboratory at BARC we have photogenerated the e^-_{aq} from the flash photolysis of various inorganic ions, e.g., $HCOO^-$ and of organic ions, Cys^- and thymine⁻ with the help of a flash photolysis method.

Next I wish to point out the usefulness of a photolysed alkaline hydrogen saturated solution as a nearly ideal source of e^-_{aq} . In this system, the reaction

20. M. S. Matheson, and J. Rabani, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 1324.

21. M. Anbar and P. Neta, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, (A), 837.

22. M. Anbar and E. J. Hart, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **71**, 3700.

23. J. Jortner and B. Shraf, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **38**, 2506.

24. M. S. Matheson, W. A. Mulac and J. Rabani, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 2613.

25. L. I. Grossweiner and H. I. Joshek, *ACS Adv. in Chem.*, 1965, **50**, 279.

26. G. Stein, *ACS Adv. in Chem.*, 1965, **50**, 230.

provides one e^-_{aq} and another results from the rapid consecutive reactions

The overall photochemical reaction

provides an impurity free source of e^-_{aq} . This reaction forms the basis for e^-_{aq} generation apparatus shown in Fig. 7. It was designed by Hart and Schmidt²⁷. We are deeply indebted to the USAEC for the loan of this equipment to us for two years.

FIG. 7 BLOCK DIAGRAM OF THE APPARATUS FOR THE PHOTOGENERATION OF HYDRATED ELECTRONS

The apparatus consists of a flash lamp, an absorption cell where e^-_{aq} is generated and a tungsten lamp, filter, photomultiplier and oscilloscope combination in the mounting system. This unit is more compact than those used in pulse radiolysis, and utilizes a "Suprasil"

Plate 1.

irradiation cell 5 cm in length and 2 cm in diameter. A xenon flash lamp provides the light pulse and a shutter-controlled built-in steady mercury lamp rids the solution of e^-_{aq} scavengers such as O_2 and organic impurities. The optical arrangement is such that it provides seven light passes, giving an absorption path length of 35 cm. The light filter combination passes 700 nm light into an RCA 7102 photomultiplier.

The complete photo flash unit is shown in Plate I. Full details of the unit are already published²⁷.

Physical properties of e^-_{aq} : Table II contains a summary of some of the physical properties of the hydrated electron²⁸

TABLE II

Physical Properties of e^-_{aq}

λ_{max} (Å)	7200
ϵ_{7200} ($M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	18500
ϵ_{5780} ($M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	10600
$d(h\nu)/dT$ (eV/deg)	-2.9×10^{-3}
Half width (eV)	0.83
Isotropic g -factor	2.0002 ± 0.0002
Hyperfine splitting	None
Line width (gauss)	0.05
$G e^-_{aq}$ (ions/100 eV)	2.6
$pK (e^-_{aq} + H_2O \rightleftharpoons H + OH^-)$	9.7
$\tau \frac{1}{2} e^-_{aq} + H_2O$ ($\mu \text{ sec}$)	780
$\tau \frac{1}{2} e^-_{aq} + H_2O$ pH 7 ($\mu \text{ sec}$)	230
Charge on ion	-1
Radius of charge distribution (Å)	2.5—3.0
Hydration energy (eV)	1.82
Diffusion constant ($\text{cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$)	4.7×10^{-5}
Equivalent conductance (mho cm^2)	177
$E^\circ (e^-_{aq} + H_3O^+ \rightarrow 1/2 H_2 + H_2O)$ (V)	2.58
$\Delta F^\circ_f; \Delta F^\circ_{hyd}$ kcal/mole	-37.2; -37.2
$\Delta H^\circ_f; \Delta H^\circ_{hyd}$	-36.3; -37.8
$S^\circ_f; S^\circ_{hyd}$ cal/mole deg	+3.1; -1.9

Taken from E. J. Hart, *Survey of Prog. Chemistry*, 5, 140, (1969).

EPR spectrum: Because of its short half life e^-_{aq} has defied detection by EPR in irradiated liquid water until recently. However, Avery²⁹ obtained an extremely narrow absorption line (< 0.5 gauss) with a g factor of 2.0002 and no hyperfine structure. It disappeared completely on the addition of e^-_{aq} scavengers.

28. E. J. Hart, *Survey Prog. Chemistry*, 1969, 5, 140.

29. E. C. Avery, J. R. Remko and B. Smaller, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, 49, 951.

Thermodynamic properties : Recent pulse radiolysis studies of highly purified slightly alkaline (pH 8–9) water saturated with hydrogen, after deaeration, have shown that the half life of the hydrated electron is at least 780 μ sec. If it is assumed to decompose by reaction

then the rate constants are known both for this reaction²⁹ (16 M⁻¹ sec⁻¹) and for the reverse³⁰ (2.3 $\times 10^7$) at 25°. From the equilibrium constant, the standard free energy ΔF can be calculated³¹. $\Delta F = +8.40$ Kcal/mole.

This now allows the calculation of the standard redox potential with respect to the hydrogen electrode, viz.,—63.9 Kcal \sim 2.77 ev. This is in excess of standard potential of H atom by 0.7 ev.

Using the same data and considering the cycle

the free energy terms for all the steps are known except $e^{-}_{aq} \rightarrow e^{-}_{gas}$, i.e., the solvation process. Hence this can be calculated. A value of —38.2 Kcal/mole is obtained³².

By analogy with the iodide ion which has a similar ΔF_h° , the entropy of solvation ΔS_h probably contributes very little to ΔH_h , hence the heat of hydration $\Delta H_h = -38.2$ Kcal/mole. This energy corresponds almost exactly to 1.72 ev, the energy of the optical absorption maximum. Thus the energy involved is the same as for the solvated electron in liquid ammonia and is rather low compared with anions in general, which suggests that the charge is somewhat diffusely spread. [For example, the heats of hydration of halide ions have been estimated as 123(F⁻), 89(Cl⁻), 81(Br⁻), 72(I⁻)]³³.

Thus the energetics indicate that in the process of hydration the electron behaves as a very large univalent ion; the effective radius has been calculated as 3.0 Å. It is not clear what this figure signifies, whether the electron is dispersed over the water molecules occupying a volume of this dimension or whether it is confined to a cavity of this size. The latter view is favoured for liquid ammonia in view of the considerable expansion when sodium is dissolved. In the more open structure of water, the actual expansion due to the electron might well be much less.

As the free energy of hydration matches well with the energy of optical absorption maximum, it is assumed that the absorption of light takes the hydrated electron from its ground state to an excited state of considerably less hydration energy, 2p.

30. E. J. Hart, S. Gordon and E. M. Fielden, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 150.

31. J. H. Baxendale, *Radiation Research Suppl.*, 1964, **4**, 139.

32. R. R. Dewald, J. L. Dye, M. Eigen, L. de Mayer, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, **39**, 2388.

33. W. M. Latimer, "Oxidation potentials", 2nd edition, 22 (1952).

Structure of hydrated electron and the process of solvation (State of electron in solution) .

We now consider the mechanism of hydration or solvation of the thermalized electron—another aspect of the theory of radiation chemistry which has been the object of great theoretical attention. The classical model of electron solvation is essentially the one based on the ‘polaron’ model developed by Davydov³⁴, Deigen³⁵ and Pekar³⁶ and more recently by Jortner³⁷. According to this model (fig. 8) the presence of the (thermal) electron in the (polar) medium causes the reorientation (or relaxation) of the otherwise randomly oriented dipoles

FIG 8

around the electron in such a manner that the positive ends of the dipoles point towards the electron and the negative ends away from it, the whole process taking about 10^{-11} sec. (in the case of water), the relaxation time for dipolar orientation. In terms of energies, this reorientation is equivalent to an orientational polarisation expressible as a function of distance r from the electron by the formula :

$$P_0 = \frac{e}{4\pi r^2} \left[\frac{1}{D_{op}} - \frac{1}{D_s} \right]$$

where e is the electronic charge and D_s and D_{op} are respectively the static and optical dielectric constants of the medium, the latter being given by the square of the refractive index. This polarisation creates a trapping potential ϕ_0 for the electron given by

$$\phi_0 = \frac{e}{r} \left[\frac{1}{D_{op}} - \frac{1}{D_s} \right]$$

The potential energy of the electron in this potential field is then

$$V_0 = -\frac{e^2}{r} \left[\frac{1}{D_{op}} - \frac{1}{D_s} \right]$$

As in the classical H-atom problem, the energies for the bound states of the electron in this potential field are given by

$$(W_n)_0 = \frac{m_e e^4}{2n^2 \hbar^2} \left[\frac{1}{D_{op}} - \frac{1}{D_s} \right]^2$$

34. A. S. Davydov, *Zhur. Eksptl. i. Teoret. Fiz.*, 1948, **18**, 913
 35. M. F. Deigen, *Zhur. Eksptl. i. Teoret. Fiz.*, 1954 **26**, 300.
 36. S. I. Pekar, *J. Phys. U.S.S.R.*, 1946, **10**, 341.
 37. J. Jortner, *Radiation Research Suppl.*, 1964, **4**, 24.

where n can have the values 1, 2, 3, ... and m_e is the rest mass of the electron. The transition of the electron from the $n = 1$ to the $n = 2$ state is considered to be responsible for its optical absorption spectrum, so that the position of the maximum is given by

$$(\Delta E)_0 = \frac{3}{4} \frac{m_e e^4}{2\hbar^2} \left[\frac{1}{D_{op}} - \frac{1}{D_s} \right]^2 = 10.21 \left[\frac{1}{D_{op}} - \frac{1}{D_s} \right]^2$$

Moorthy and Shankar³⁸ have recently reconsidered both the kinetic as well as the energetic aspects of the solvated electron on the basis of the polaron model. In what follows we adopt their approach.

One can look at the kinetic aspect in two ways. The mean displacement $(\bar{X}^2)_{\tau}^{\ddagger}$ of the thermal electron during the relaxation time of the matrix dipoles is given by Einstein's formula for Brownian motion :

$$(\bar{X}^2)_{\tau}^{\ddagger} = [1/3kT_{\tau}/\pi\eta r_e]^2$$

where k is the Boltzman constant, T the temperature ($^{\circ}\text{K}$) of the medium, η its viscosity and r_e the radius of the electron, which can be computed to be 2.8×10^{-13} cm on the basis of the assumption that the mass of the electron is entirely of electromagnetic origin. For water at $T = 298^{\circ}\text{K}$, $\eta = 0.894 \times 10^{-2}$ dyne sec. cm^2 and $\tau = 10^{-11}$ sec., so that $(\bar{X}^2)_{\tau}^{\ddagger}$ turns out to be 420 \AA , a distance spanning about 170 water molecules. In the alternative approach one can equate the kinetic energy of the thermal electron with the average kinetic energy of the medium molecules : $\frac{1}{2} m_e v^2 = \frac{3}{4} kT$ so that the average displacement of the electron during the period of dipolar orientation is given by $(\bar{c}^2)_{\tau}^{\ddagger} = (3kT/m_e)_{\tau}^{\ddagger}$ and this works out to be 11630 \AA for water at 298°K . Thus, by the time the matrix dipoles have oriented around the 'electron' the latter has moved away from its original site several hundred molecular distances away. The situation worsens as one goes to lower temperatures so much so that in frozen systems, for which the dipolar relaxation times are virtually infinity the thermal electron would have drifted out of the medium altogether. On the basis of either of the above formulae, one can compute that, in order to confine the electron during the period of dipolar orientation within one molecular distance from the origin, the relaxation time must be much smaller, viz., 10^{-15} — 10^{-16} sec. This time is much too short for molecular motion, but only electronic displacements in the molecules are possible. This implies that the polarisation which can bind a thermal electron in a potential well is the electronic (or optical) polarisation and not the orientational polarisation as conceived in the original polaron theory.

Another approach is to consider the energetics of the polaron on the basis of both electronic and orientational polarisations, as well as total polarisation. This has led to even more interesting results. Without going into details, which are similar to those of the classical polaron based on orientational polarisation only, the optical transition energy on the basis of electronic polarisation and total polarisation would be given by :

$$(\Delta E)_e = 10.21 \left[1 - \frac{1}{D_{op}} \right]^2$$

$$(\Delta E)_t = 10.21 \left[1 - \frac{1}{D_s} \right]^2$$

In table III $(\Delta E)_o$ and $(\Delta E)_e$, $(\Delta E)_t$ computed for a number of similar polar systems are compared with the experimental values, from which it is seen that the $(\Delta E)_e$'s agree with experimental values at least as well as, if not better than, the $(\Delta E)_o$'s whereas the $(\Delta E)_t$'s are far too high. For water and ice for which static dielectric constant and refractive index data are available over a wide range of temperature, Moorthy and Shankar have also calculated the $(\Delta E)_o$'s and $(\Delta E)_e$'s at different temperatures in order to compare with the experimentally observed variation of ΔE with temperature which is now available for both these phases from pulse radiolysis studies. This comparison is shown in Figs. 9 and 9a. One can see from these figures that the optical transition energy of the 'hydrated' electron calculated on the basis of electronic polarisation only varies with temperature in the same direction as the experimental values, the slopes being -1.1×10^{-3} eV/°C and -2.9×10^{-3} eV/°C respectively in water and -0.3×10^{-3} eV/°C and -0.93×10^{-3} eV/°C respectively in ice, whereas $(\Delta E)_o$ exhibits an opposite trend (slope = $\sim 0.49 \times 10^{-3}$ eV/°C in water; positive, but widely varying over the temperature range studies, in ice

TABLE III

Compound	$RI = (D_{op})^{\frac{1}{2}}$	D_s	$(\Delta E)_o$ eV	$(\Delta E)_e$ eV	$(\Delta E)_t$ eV	$(\Delta E)_{expt}$ eV
Ethylene Glycol	1.43	38.7	2.19	2.67	9.69	2.14
Methanol	1.33	33.6	2.93	1.93	9.61	1.97
Ethanol	1.36	25.1	2.56	2.15	9.41	1.77
<i>n</i> -Propanol	1.38	20.8	2.32	2.30	9.25	1.68
Iso-Propanol	1.38	19.0	2.28	2.30	9.16	1.51
Water	1.33	80.0	3.12	1.93	9.95	1.72
Ammonia	1.33	22.0	2.76	1.93	9.30	0.84

FIG. 9

FIG 9 (a)

The consideration of both the kinetics as well as the energetics of the solvated electron on the basis of the 'polaron' model thus leads to the conclusion that only the electronic polarisation, and not the orientational polarisation as used to be believed till now, is of significance in the process of 'solvation' of the electron and this conclusion is of even greater importance in the case of non-polar media and frozen systems, where in also there is evidence³⁹ for the formation of solvated electrons. Thus, in non-polar media, there are no permanent molecular dipoles, whereas in frozen systems the relaxation times are so very long that the dipoles are, so to say, frozen in and cannot orient at all around an electron introduced into the medium. Hence, the experimentally observed bound states must arise through electron trapping in potential wells created by electronic polarisation only.

Recently, Jortner⁴⁰ has carried out calculations based on a self-consistent field polaron model in which the additional electron and the medium electrons are treated on an equal basis. In the limit of zero cavity radius, this model predicts an optical transition energy of 1.35 eV for the hydrated electron at 25°, whereas the experimental value is 1.72 eV, and the agreement at larger cavity radii is poorer still.

A physical picture of the hydrated electron has been given by Natori and Watanabe⁴¹ in their tetrahedral model. This is based on the fact that liquid water has micro crystalline regions where the tetrahedral structure of ice is retained, a central water molecule linked by hydrogen bonds to four water molecules at the corners of a regular tetrahedron (fig. 10). When an electron enters a defect site wherein the water molecule in the center of the tetrahedron is missing, the electron causes orientation of two of the corner water molecules in such a way that the positive (H) ends (one of each) of these water dipoles also point towards the electron. The electron finds itself trapped in this state. The optical transition energy for such a species has been calculated to be 0.8 eV whereas the experimental value is 1.72 eV, at 25°.

FIG 10

39. J. B. Gallivan and W. H. Hamill, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1966, **44**, 2378.

40. J. Jortner, in *Radiation Chemistry of Aqueous Systems*, G. Stein, Ed., Weizmann Science Press of Israel, "Jerusalem, 1968, p. 91.

41. M. Natori and T. Watanabe, *J. Phys. Soc. (Japan)*, 1966, **21**, 1573.

In a more recent calculation Natoari⁴² takes the distance (1) from the electron at the centre of the tetrahedron to the oxygen atom at the corner as a variable parameter and also considers the possibility that the presence of the electron instead of the water molecule at the centre of the tetrahedron would lengthen the O-H bonds of the corner molecules because of the higher effective charge on the e^- ($-e$) as compared to that on the O atom in the H_2O molecule ($-0.652e$). They find the best agreement (calculated and experimental ΔE values about the same) with O-H bond length of 1.1 \AA , H-O-H angle of 116° and $l = 2.62 \text{ \AA}$. Temperature dependence of ΔE has not been worked out on this model, but could be attributed to possible expansion of the tetrahedron with increasing temperature as Natoari finds that E decreases with increasing l . This structural model would also suffer from the same draw-back as the classical polaron model, viz., that by the time the water molecules have oriented, the electron would have moved considerable distance away, unless the attractive potential between the electron and two of the corner water molecules which, even prior to the introduction of the electron, are oriented with their positive ends pointing to the center of the tetrahedron, is sufficient to localise the electron, the orientation of the water molecules at the other two corners taking place only subsequently.

Reactions of the hydrated electron: Although e^-_{aq} has only been known for 10 years some 800 of its rate constants have already been measured⁴³; more than the combined sum of the H and OH rate constants. Most of these have been obtained by following the decay of e^-_{aq} absorption band by the technique of pulse radiolysis where conditions for setting up a pseudo-first order kinetics for reactions are simple. Its reactions may be studied at 10^{-5} or even $10^{-6} M$ solute concentrations since the decay of e^-_{aq} may be followed from an initial concentration of 10^{-7} – $10^{-8} M$ down to $10^{-9} M$.

Some representative reactions of e^-_{aq} with inorganic molecules and ions appear in Fig. 11. The hydrated electron lowers the charge on the positive ion by one unit. Thus Cu^{+2} , Zn^{+2} from Cu^{+1} and Zn^{+1} respectively. Their rate constants range from 4×10^7 for Mn^{+2} to 3.9×10^{10} for Pb^{+2} . One very interesting feature of these reduced ions is their transient absorption band centred at 3100 \AA .⁴⁴

Fig 11 Hydrated electron rate constants of some inorganic compounds

42. M. Natoari, *J. Phys. Soc. (Japan)*, 1968, **24**, 913.

43. M. Anbar and P. Neta. *Int. J. Appl. Rad. Isotopes*, 1967, **18**, 493.

44a. J. H. Baxendale, E. M. Fielden and J. P. Keene, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1965, **A286**, 320.

44b. G. B. Adams, J. H. Baxendale and J. W. Boag, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 241.

Of the rare earth ions, Eu^{+3} , Yb^{+3} and Sm^{+3} are the most reactive. Each of these ions possesses stable divalent state. The remaining ions except Tm^{+3} and Ho^{+3} have rate constants of the order of $10^8 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. So while the rate constants of Eu^{+3} , Sm^{+3} follow the same trend expected from their electrode potentials, the electronic structure and the charge distribution of the ion must be important additional factors.

Since all the reactions of e^-_{aq} are either electron attachment or dissociative electron transfer processes one might expect that the availability of a suitable low energy molecular orbital governs the reactivity of a solute. The molecular radical anions formed from stable molecules like O_2 , CO_2 etc. display transient absorption spectra that may be further used to study their properties.

Figure 12 shows some examples from organic compounds. In case of CCl_4 , CHCl_3 etc. a simple dissociative electron addition takes place

In $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{I}$, I^- formation accompanies hydrated electron disappearance atleast on a micro-second scale⁴⁵. In each case electron attachment reaction is diffusion controlled.

Profound alterations in activity occur upon complexing of the ion. The aquo complexes of Al^{+3} , Cr^{+3} , Zn^{+3} are much more reactive than their corresponding hydroxy analogues. According to Hart⁴⁶, this is attributed to the fact that compared to H_2O , OH permits less efficient channelling of the electron to the central atom.

FIG 12 Hydrated electron rate constants of some organic compounds

Aquo and ethylenediamine complexes display the highest reactivity. In these compounds halide addition to the complex even though it reduces the positive charge on the ion, increases its reactivity. For example, $\text{Cr}(\text{en})\text{Cl}_2^+$ with a rate constant of 7.1×10^{10} compares with $\text{Cr}(\text{en})_2^{+3}$, whose rate constant is $5.3 \times 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. In most ions the ligands transport the electrons to the central atom according to the following sequence.

45. J. K. Thomas, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **71**, 1919.

46. M. Anbar and E. J. Hart, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 271.

This sequence parallels their ability to channel an electron in outer sphere oxidation reduction processes.

Most of the negative ions, F^- , Cl^- , CN^- , etc., have completely filled shells and hence are inert. But highly reactive are the dichromate and permanganate ions. e^-_{aq} reduces them instantaneously

This reaction has been verified spectrophotometrically by the simultaneous disappearance of the MnO_4^- ion and the hydrated e^-_{aq} with the accompanying formation⁴⁷ of MnO_4^{2-} .

Reactions of e^-_{aq} with organic solutes : The saturated hydrocarbons as would be expected are inert towards hydrated electron. Alcohols, ethers, esters and amines are also unreactive. The $COOH$ group gives some reactivity, while the COO^- group is much less effective. The carbonyl group has very high reactivity. The alkyl halides are particularly reactive with reactivity towards e^-_{aq} increasing in the order of $F \ll Cl < Br < I$. Anbar and Hart⁴⁸ found that this order correlates with halogen polarizability but not with halogen electron affinity or with the polarization of C^+-X bond.

A very interesting study points out the correlation of the effect of substituents on the reactivity of aromatic compounds with their Hammett's function⁴⁹. The Hammett equation

$$\log [k_{C_6H_5X}/k_{C_6H_6}] = \rho\sigma$$

achieves a quantitative evaluation of the reactivity of substituted benzenes toward nucleophilic or electrophilic reagents.

Fig 13 η as a function of σ of Hammett's equation [Reprinted from Anbar and Hart, *J. Am. Chem Soc* 86, 5633 (1964)]

$$\eta = \log [k_{C_6H_5X} + e^-_{aq} / k_{C_6H_6} + e^-_{aq}]$$

47. E. M. Fielden and E. J. Hart, *Radiation Res.*, 1967, **32**, 564.

48. M. Anbar and E. J. Hart, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **69**, 271.

49. M. Anbar and E. J. Hart, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **68**, 5633.

Here σ shows the effect of the substituent on reactivity and ρ is a constant for a given reaction.

While the rate constant of benzene is only about $10^7 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, the effect of electron withdrawing and electron donating group is very pronounced. In these compounds the rate constant varies from 4×10^6 for the phenolate ions to 3×10^{10} for nitrobenzene

A plot of Hammett's σ function is linear with η defined as

$$\log [k_{C_6H_5X+e^-_{aq}} / k_{C_6H_6+e^-_{aq}}]$$

Reactions with monomers : For the last couple of years our group at BARC has been actively engaged in the study of radiation induced polymerisation⁵⁰. It was found that radiation induced polymerisation can be either free radical in nature or cationic or anionic. In the anionic type the initiating species is a negative ion formed by the addition of an electron to the monomer molecule

For the correlation of the polymerisability of different monomers by radiation by the anionic mechanism, one needs to know the rate constant for this initial addition reaction. Table IV shows many of the rate constants recently determined in our laboratory with the help of the photo electron generation unit⁵¹

TABLE IV*

*Rate constants for the reaction of the solvated electron
with different monomers at pH 11*

Monomer	Rate constant $\text{l.mole}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$
Acrylonitrile	1.0×10^{10}
Methyl acrylate	9.4×10^9
Ethyl acrylate	8.7×10^9
Methyl methacrylate	6.3×10^9
Vinyl isobutyl ether	$< 10^7$
N-vinyl pyrrolidone	2.0×10^9
Vinyl acetate	1.7×10^9
Vinyl benzoate	7.3×10^9
Methacrylic acid	3.0×10^9
Acrylamide	9.7×10^9
<i>s</i> -Trioxane	$\sim 10^6$
Ethylene	2.5×10^9
Styrene	1.1×10^{10}

50a. K. N. Rao, C. Gopinathan, P. N. Moorthy, M. H. Rao and Vijay Kumar, BARC, 331 (1968).

b. K. N. Rao, P. N. Moorthy, M. H. Rao, Vijay Kumar and C. Gopinathan, BARC, 369 (1968).

51. P. N. Moorthy, Vijay Kumar, K. N. Rao—Private Communication (1970), Work done at Chemistry Division, BARC.

From this one can see that a nonvinylic monomer such as *s*-trioxane is rather unreactive; so is ethylene itself. But styrene in which the ethylenic double bond is conjugated with the benzene ring exhibits high reactivity. The acrylate, methacrylate, acrylamide, acrylonitrile all show a high reactivity because of the conjugation of the strongly electron attracting carbonyl or cyano group with the ethylenic double bond

Among these, methyl acrylate is more reactive than methyl methacrylate, because in the latter electron donating methyl group reduces somewhat the effect of the electron attracting COOCH_3 group. Similarly methacrylic acid which was present as methacrylate ion in the pH 11 matrix is found to be less reactive

When the carbonyl group is not directly conjugated with the ethylenic double bond as in vinyl acetate or vinyl pyrolidone, the reactivity is less as compared to a compound with direct conjugation of the carbonyl group. If the compound has another electron attracting group the reactivity further increases as can be seen by a comparison of the rate constants for vinyl acetate and vinyl benzoate.

Table V shows another example of attempts to correlate the reactivities of organic compounds towards e^-_{aq} with molecular structural details. Here we have tabulated the rate constants of many perfluoro carbons with e^-_{aq} obtained again at BARC⁵². On careful examination, one fact clearly emerges that electron reactivity seems to be very much dependent upon the geometric configuration of the molecule. We found that all the cyclic perfluoro carbons react much faster than the corresponding straight chain compounds. These

TABLE V

Rate constants of e^-_{aq} with perfluorocarbons

Effect of molecular structure on electron trapping

		$k(\text{M}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1})$
Perfluoro <i>n</i> -Hexane	C_6F_{14}	$< 10^7$
Perfluoro Cyclohexane	C_6F_{12}	1.2×10^{10}
Perfluoro <i>n</i> -Butane	C_4F_{10}	$< 10^7$
Perfluoro Cyclobutane	C_4F_8	4.4×10^{10}
Perfluoro Benzene	C_6F_6	7.2×10^{10}
Perfluoro Biphenyl	$(\text{C}_6\text{F}_5)_2$	9.0×10^{10}
Perfluoro Octane	C_8F_{18}	$< 10^9$
Perfluoro Cyclo octane	C_8F_{16}	3.2×10^{10}

A concept of intramolecular electrostatic electron trap is being introduced.

52. J. P. Mittal and L. J. Mittal—Private communication (1970), Work done at Chemistry Division, BARC.

results have corroborated the earlier results⁵³ where a concept of intramolecular electrostatic electron traps was introduced. It appears that in all the cyclic fluorocarbons some kind of potential well is established electrostatically giving rise to an electrostatic cavity for the electron to occupy. Further theoretical implications of this work are under study.

Reaction with biological compounds : Figure 14 gives hydrated electron rate constants of some compounds of biological interest. Some very valuable information of use in radiation biology is evident. The purine and pyrimidine constituents of nucleic acids are highly reactive. Adenosine, cytidine, 5-methylcytosine, purine and thymine possess rate constants of the order of $10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. Consequently, they attest to their diffusion controlled nature and that reactions occur on each encounter.

FIG 14 Hydrated electron rate constants of some amino acids, purines and pyrimidines

On the other hand, the amino acid constituents of the protein generally possess very low reactivity. The simple amino acids such as glycine, alanine, proline, etc., have rate constants less than $10^7 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. However, substituted amino acids such as phenyl alanine, histidine and those containing sulphur groups, such as cysteine and cystine have reactivities

TABLE VI

Compounds Studied	Conc. range $\text{M/L} \times 10^6$	$k \times \text{M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$			$k \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ (Photogeneration with Corning CS-930 filter)
		Photogeneration	pH	Pulse radiolysis	
Cysteine-HCl	28-100	3.5×10^8	11.0	7.5×10^7 (4) at pH = 11.6	7.65 ± 0.7
Cysteine	50-90	3.7×10^8	11.0	$< 7.5 \times 10^7$ (4) at pH = 11.0	4.48 ± 0.5
Reduced Glutathione	60-110	1.5×10^8	11.0	—	7.73 ± 0.9
Cystine	0.5 to 1.2	$2.46 \pm 0.3 \times 10^9$	11.0	2.5×10^8 (4) at pH 10.7 3.0×10^8 (4) at pH 12.0	—
Oxidised Glutathione	0.5 to 1.4	$1.15 \pm 0.15 \times 10^9$	11.0	—	—

53. J. P. Mittal and W. F. Libby, *Nature*, 1968, 220, 1029.

of the order of 10^8 and $10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. Consequently, in any aqueous medium containing proteins the probable point of attack will be the substituted amino acids or on the sulphur or disulphide bonds of the proteins.

It is interesting to note here that recently while checking some of the rate constants of e^-_{aq} with sulphydryl and disulphide compounds with the above mentioned photo electron generation unit at Chemistry Division, BARC, it has been found⁵⁴ that with almost all the sulphydryl compounds the rate constants we were getting were higher compared to those previously reported by pulse radiolysis (Table VI)

In addition to this it was found that the peak height of the signal increased with the addition of increasing concentrations of solutes. This was explained according to the following argument.

The pK values for cysteine etc. are ~ 10.5 and it has been reported that at pH 11.0 almost all the CySH is ionised

We also know that CyS^- absorbs strongly upto 250 nm and hence it was postulated that when flashed with UV light of the Xe flash lamp the following reaction might be occurring producing additional hydrated electrons.

This was then checked by placing a CS-930 filter in front of the cell so as to prevent the passage of light below 225 nm, which is mainly responsible for the ionisation of OH^- . The decay curves (d) for the pure matrix without CS-930 filter and (b) with the filter in figure-15 clearly illustrate that hydrated electrons produced due to OH^- ions are being cut off completely by the filter.

The decay curve (c) after injecting small quantities ($\sim 50 \mu\text{M}$) of cystein HCl in the matrix shows clearly that the e^-_{aq} are definitely produced due to the above reaction, although they decay simultaneously. From these decay curves then the rate constants have been obtained by the standard method and tabulated in the last column of Table VI. Comparison of column 6 and 5 clearly indicates that the rate constants for cystein HCl and cystein are in good agreement with the reported values by pulse radiolysis technique.

FIG. 15

Similar results of photogeneration of e^-_{aq} from the photolysis of thymine anion have also been obtained recently in our laboratory⁵⁵

Applications. Since the solvated electron was discovered, great strides have been made in our knowledge of radiation chemistry. But this discovery has made an even, greater contribution to science in general and physical chemistry in particular. Were e^-_{aq} found only in irradiated water, its usefulness to science would be quite restricted, but as we have seen that not only is it a common product of aqueous photochemical reactions, it also participates in many chemical reactions (e.g., ammoniated e^- in the Birch reduction of organic compounds).

It is bound to play very significant role in two places. (i) Reinvestigation of "established" chemical mechanism. Entirely new data has now become available for theoretical chemists studying the dynamics of electron-transfer and electrode reactions. Many of the organic reactions which have so far been understood only in terms of free radicals etc. will have to be revised. (ii) Its role in radiation biology.

Although reactions of the hydrated electrons with compounds are non-specific the pathway is open for its use as a novel, highly reactive, analytical reagent⁵⁶. Because of its very high molar extinction coefficient, it can be routinely used at concentrations as low as 10^{-9} M. Consequently, many compounds possessing rate constants greater than 10^9 M⁻¹ sec⁻¹ can be analysed in nanomolar concentration. Figure 16 shows examples of some such solutes

In addition to the determinations of rate constants of e^-_{aq} reactions, the immediate products of these reactions with a number of solutes, both inorganic (O_2 , I_2 etc.) and organic can be characterised either by spectral or indirect evidences. In many cases the species resulting e^-_{aq} reaction would themselves be unstable ions and radicals. Learning about their reactivity and dynamics is itself opening up an entirely virgin field for research.

Fig 16 Calibration curves for some e^-_{aq} scavengers at pH 11

$t_{1/2}$ Half-life with scavenger, $t_{1/2}^0$ Half-life of matrix

55. J. P. Mittal and L. J. Mittal—Private Communication (1970)—Work done at Chemistry Division, BARC.

56. E. J. Hart and E. M. Fielden, *ACS Adv. in Chem.*, 1965, 50, 253

The following are a few examples of some very recent work from our laboratory at BARC bearing on this line⁵⁷. Here we have studied the reactivities of such unstable transient as HO₂, O₂⁻, C₆H₁₁O₂ and COO⁻.

*Reactions of organic peroxy radicals*⁵⁷: Produced *in situ* in the radiolysis of air saturated aqueous solutions of cyclohexane.

* L. V. Shastri—(Ph.D. thesis, 1970)—Work done at Chemistry Division, BARC.

Fig. 17

The kinetic analysis of the pH dependence of organic peroxide yields showed that O₂⁻ reacts about 600 times faster than HO₂ with C₆H₁₁O₂ radicals.

*Reactions of COO⁻ radical ion*⁵⁷: Radiolysis of divalent metal ions such as Cu⁺², Co⁺², Ni⁺² and Cd⁺² and formate ions.

It was shown that formation ions can reduce divalent ions all the way to metal through COO⁻ ions.

In view of its high reactivity with carbon dioxide it may be the primary reducing species involved in photosynthesis. An example of the involvement of e⁻_{aq} in radiation and photobiology again comes from some of the recent work from our laboratory at BARC. It has long been postulated and experimentally verified that thymine in aqueous solutions or in solid state (in presence of moisture) on photolysis and radiolysis gets destroyed by adding H atoms at 5, 6 double bond, giving rise to a radical which may then be involved in the genetic damage to cells through an interstrand dimer formation. It has now been established⁵⁸ that this reaction proceeds via a hydrated electron adduct

57. L. V. Shastri—Ph.D. Thesis submitted to Bombay University, 1970. Work done at Chemistry Division, BARC.

Untangling of this has become possible only after the rate constant of thymine towards e^-_{aq} was determined and compared with H atoms. This opens up new vistas for working on the molecular mechanisms of radiation protection.

To the radiation biologists it will also be significant that purines and pyrimidines, constituent of DNA, react much faster with e^-_{aq} than do the amino acids of proteins. Almost surely DNA becomes the seat of e^-_{aq} attack during irradiation, although there are some very reactive bonds in the proteins. Thus it may help to explain the beneficial effects of radiation therapy in the treatment of cancer. And, since radiation sterilization is becoming increasingly important in the preservation of food, a knowledge of the activity of hydrated electrons with the constituents affecting taste, flavour and odour may help in making these processes more practicable. Work on these lines is already under way at BARC. In conclusion, I would like to quote from the discoverer of the absorption spectrum of e^-_{aq} , Dr. E. J. Hart, "In the hydrated electron the kineticists dream has been realised". We are still scratching the surface learning of the potentials of this very reactive "new element" of mass zero, atomic number zero and electric charge-1.

58. J. P. Mittal—Ph.D. Thesis, University of Notre Dame, USA 1967 and work done at Chemistry Division, BARC.